

Reversing the Arago spot

A solution to the IPT-problem "The bright spot"

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Code for this project available on Github: <https://github.com/vrogly/The-bright-spot>

Abstract

The Arago-Poisson spot is a diffractive phenomena typically associated with the early experiments verifying the wave like nature of light. This study has investigated diffraction in the context of the Arago-Poisson spot. Theoretical and experimental results suggest that for simple shapes, the two-dimensional projected area of a three-dimensional shape is sufficient to determine its diffractive shadow. Based on this observation, a simplified two dimensional model centered around Huygen sources originating from the edges of a shape was proposed. This model was verified with simulations using the Rayleigh-Sommerfeld integral and experimental data. The diffractive pattern of simulations and experiments were reversed using the Hybrid Input Output and Error Reduction phase retrieval algorithm implemented by the Python package Pyphase (HIO-ER). The simplified model was able to predict general features of the diffraction patterns of the shadow. This information could be used to construct an algorithm which reverses the shape of an object based on such general features. HIO-ER was able to reverse the contours of simulated diffraction patterns with high precision but was not as successful with the experimental data. This study identifies the quality of the experimental data as the main reason for this and the HIO-ER is thought to be able to reverse experimental data from a more refined setup.

Keywords: Arago-Poisson spot, diffraction, phase retrieval algorithms

1 Introduction

The International Physics Tournament (IPT) is an international competition in experimental physics where students from around the world try to solve open-ended physics problems. The following problem from the 2024 edition forms the basis of this report,

There is a famous phenomenon in wave optics called the Arago-Poisson spot where a bright spot is created in the middle of the shadow of a spherical object when one shines coherent light on it. By shining the light on other types of solids (e.g. cubes, cylinders, etc.) one gets different patterns to appear in the shadow of the object. What information about the geometry of a solid can be obtained by analyzing the pattern in its shadow? [1]

1.1 Diffraction

The Arago spot is a diffractive phenomena [2]. Propagation of a plane wave, such as a laser, is described by the wave equation and more specifically the Helmholtz equation [3]. Solving this differential equation is, however, too computationally expensive for the purposes of this study. Instead it could be described with the Huygen-Fresnel principle which says that a wave front is composed of a set of light sources emitting spherical waves [4]. When a light beam is blocked by a two dimensional object, the point sources right behind the blockage will be blocked from further propagating with the object acting as a mask. This field can then be propagated and is accurate for near field diffraction [5]. Summing the contributions from these point sources at a propagated plane is thus described by the Rayleigh-Sommerfeld integral,

$$U(x,y,z) = \frac{1}{i\lambda} \iint U(x',y',0) \frac{ze^{ik\sqrt{(x-x')^2+(y-y')^2+z^2}}}{(x-x')^2+(y-y')^2+z^2} dx'dy' \quad (1)$$

where a shape is encoded as $U(x',y',0) = 0$ and the rest of the initial field described by the initial profile of the incoming plane wave, which in this study will be a Gaussian distribution [5].

1.2 The Poisson-Arago spot

A simple explanation for the Poisson-Arago spot is that a spherical object obstructs an incoming laser which interferes with the edges of the sphere and create Huygen sources. These Huygen sources subsequently interfere with each other, and create an interference pattern on a detector plane with local maxima along nodal lines. This interference will be strongest in the middle, symmetry line, which creates the spot. This is shown in figure 1.

1.3 The phase problem

It is a common situation in optical imaging to measure the intensity at a plane after subjecting an object to a light source. The question then becomes what properties of the object can be reconstructed based on the information about the initial light source and the intensity at the measuring plane. Since the measurement only yields information about the intensity of the light and not the phase, the phase has to be reconstructed in order to propagate the light backwards and get the intensity in the object plane. This is called the phase problem [6]. There are several algorithms developed for this purpose. One of the most famous ones are called the Error Reduction algorithm (ER). This works by iteratively performing the inverse propagation on a guess and substituting the intensity field but keeping the phase field. A slight modification of this algorithm is called the Hybrid Input Output Algorithm (HIO) that is found to have better convergence [6].

Figure 1: A simplified explanation of the Arago-spot phenomena using Huygen sources. The blue arrows through nodal points corresponds to maximums in the detector plane.

2 Theoretical justifications and derivations

The original problem statement exemplifies different three-dimensional objects that all are extrusions of two dimensional masks, e.g. the cylinder being an extruded circle. It is unclear whether there is any difference between the spots formed by a three-dimensional shape and a corresponding two-dimensional mask. This will be discussed at length in this section and investigated experimentally.

2.1 Justification for 2D reduction

A simplifying assumption is made where the interference pattern within the shadow only will be able to reverse an three-dimensional objects two-dimensional shadow. This will be justified experimentally and modelled in section 2.1.2.

2.1.1 Rotating an fixed object

Assuming that the shadow of an object can be reconstructed based on the formed spots, the question still remains what information that shadow contains about the original 3D shape. This is an area of research in of it self and is not necessarily related to optics. As an example Liu et al. [7] presents an generative model to reverse an objects shape based on a single snapshot of its shadow with promising results. Thus, consecutively rotating the three dimensional object and reconstructing the shadow at all angles would yield data to feed into such an algorithm. This will not be a focus of this report.

2.1.2 Identical 2D shadows

A simple experiment to investigate whether the three-dimensional profile or just its two-dimensional shadow is relevant is to compare the interference pattern of two different three-dimensional objects with the same projected area. An example of this is shown in figure 2.

Using the aforementioned simplification that the plane wave acts as a Huygen source at the edge of the object, figure 2 shows the propagation of these waves to a detector plane. Using the path difference as a measure for constructive or destructive interference,

$$\Delta L_{\text{total}} = \left(\delta + \sqrt{(w/2 - y_D)^2 + (x_D - \delta)^2} \right) - \sqrt{(w/2 + y_D)^2 + (x_D)^2} \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: A simple experiment to with constant projected area but different three dimensional structure.

and similarly to the derivation of the diffraction formula for a single slit, there will be local brightness maximums whenever $\Delta L_{\text{total}} = n\lambda$, which corresponds to the two spherical waves being in phase with each other at that point. Now $\Delta L_{\text{total}}(x_D, y_D) - n\lambda = 0$ forms an algebraic curve which shows the location y_D of the n th maximum after propagating the distance x_D . With $w = 0$ this is the same setup as discussed in figure 1. Numerical calculations of the model with the measures of the experimental setup used in section 3.1 are shown in figure 3. The difference between y_D/w at $x_D = 0.1$ m for $\delta = 0$ and $\delta = w$ is less than 1% which suggests that two objects with the same projected area will have the same interference patterns.

Figure 3: The solution y_D to $\Delta L_{\text{total}} = n\lambda$ using 2 plotted with comparable values to the experiments, $w = 1.5$ mm and $\lambda = 532$ nm. The deviations are large for small values of x_D , values that are much smaller than what is used in experiments, otherwise the difference is negligible.

2.2 Simplified model

Using a similar argumentation as the model above, as in figure 1 and 2, a simplified model predicting the appearance of bright spots can be proposed. It is expected that some information of the interference pattern would only depend on the shape itself meaning it would be independent of propagation distance. In that case the distance travelled by the a Huygen source from the edge would only depend on the distance from the edge of the mask $\partial M(\vec{r})$ to the point $\vec{x} = (x_D, y_D)$. The phase of the contributions at this points will determine if \vec{x} receives a net destructive interference or constructive interference, meaning that it would be a bright spot. Formally, the intensity at a point $I(x, y)$ inside the mask M described by the curve $\partial M(\vec{r})$ is the sum of contributions of phase differences and using the cosine to find the interference intensity yields

$$\begin{aligned} I(x, y) &= \max_{\phi_{\text{ref}} \in [-\pi, \pi]} \left(\frac{1}{|\partial M|} \oint_{\partial M} \cos(\phi_{\partial M}(\vec{x}, \vec{r}) - \phi_{\text{ref}}) dr \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{|\partial M|} \left(\left(\oint_{\partial M} \cos(\phi_{\partial M}) dr \right)^2 + \left(\oint_{\partial} M \sin(\phi_{\partial M}) dr \right)^2 \right)^{1/2}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where the initial integral was rewritten using two trigonometric identities and

$$\phi_{\partial M}(\vec{x}, \vec{r}) = 2\pi \frac{|\vec{x}(x, y) - \vec{r}(x, y)|}{\lambda} - 2\pi n, \quad (4)$$

for some integer n that shifts the angle into the interval $(-\pi, \pi)$. The integral is challenging to discretize as $\phi_{\partial M}$ contains two length scales, both λ which is in the order of hundreds of nanometers and $\vec{x} - \vec{r}$ which is in the order of millimeters. This is further described in section 3.3.

3 Method

The investigation was split into two parts, generating diffraction patterns for a wide range of shapes using experiments and simulations, and reversing the shapes, using a the proposed simplified model and algorithms from the literature.

3.1 Experimental setup

A schematic view of the setup is showed in figure 4. A incoming laser with wavelength $\lambda = 532$ nm, a 3 mm beam waist and 100 mW effect were passed through a convex lens with focal length 25.4 mm. The lens acts as a beam expander. After 290 mm either a three-dimensional object or a thin plastic film with a two dimensional mask was placed in the beam. Then the light was allowed to propagate 2570 mm to a piece of paper. This paper was then photographed from an angle with a mobile camera. The size of the shadow was effectively expanded by a factor ten.

Figure 4: Experimental setup with measures marked in the figure. The beam wavelength was 532 nm and had an effect of 100 mW

The 2D masks were constructed by printing them with a commercial ink printer on the same transparent film twice to increase the contrast. The masks are shown in figure 5a.

(a) Shapes tested in experiments. Size of initial circle is 1.5 mm and the rest of the shapes are drawn to scale. (b) Shapes tested in simulations and theoretical predictions. Size of initial circle is 1.5 mm and the rest of the shapes are drawn to scale.

Figure 5: Full list of investigated shapes in experiments, theoretical predictions and simulations.

3.2 Simulations

The Python package `diffractions` [8] was used to simulate the propagation. The simulation parameters were for a scenario similar to figure 4 but for shorter distances. The scalar field being propagated had the shape of a Gaussian beam with beam waist of 1.75 mm and peak amplitude 1, it was placed in a 10 mm × 10 mm window with the shapes in figure 5b as 1.5 mm wide masks placed in the center. This was discretized with the resolution 2048 × 2048. For each shape this initial scalar field was propagated 50 mm, 100 mm, 150 mm, 200 mm, 250 mm, 500 mm and 10 m using the Rayleigh-Sommerfeld Diffraction Integral, i.e. equation 1.

3.3 Discretization of theoretical model

The theoretical model requires the parametrization of the shapes to compute the integral in equation 1. Since λ is several orders of magnitude smaller than the length dimensions of the difference $|\vec{x}-\vec{r}|$, ϕ_γ will be difficult to calculate numerically. The use of raster graphics where the size of a pixel is much longer than λ further complicates this. The implementation to calculate the integral was to initially down sample the image to 250×250 pixels, tracing the contours of the image and calculating the path differences in equation 4. Then the path difference was rescaled to physical dimensions and were rounded to the nearest $0.1 \mu\text{m}$. Using this, the rest of equation 3 was calculated. The implementation is available in the linked code.

3.4 Applying phase algorithms

The algorithm that was chosen to reverse the phase for simulated data was to perform three iterations of the Hybrid Input-Output algorithm [9] then two iterations of the Error Reduction algorithm [10] and repeat that processes a total of two times as implemented by the Python package `pyphase` [11]. The entire process is called HIO-ER. For experimental data this was changed to 45, 5 and 4 respectively, the defaults used by [11]. The sensitivity of the algorithm was further investigated by cropping and downscaling the simulated image and applying generated shot noise, using algorithm developed by [12], to the simulated data.

4 Results

In this chapter the results from experiments and simulations are shown. These are compared to the theoretical predictions and thereafter fed into a phase retrieval algorithm. In the end, the sensitivity of the phase retrieval algorithm is investigated¹.

4.1 Experiments

The experimental pictures have been converted to gray scale to make them more easily compared to the simulated results.

4.1.1 Three dimensional objects

Figure 6 show the three dimensional objects that were placed in the experimental setup shown in figure 4. Figure 6a and 6c were glued on a plastic film and figure 6b and 6d were held with a pair of tweezers. A dot is visible in figure 6a and 6b which both have the same two dimensional shadow.

¹Only a fraction of all renders and experiments are presented here. For access to the full set of data, contact the author.

(a) Ball bearing with radius 3 mm diameter 3 mm glued to a thin piece of plastic film. (b) Screw head with diameter 4 mm held with a pair of tweezers. (c) Capacitor with side length 5 mm glued to a thin piece of plastic film. (d) Cap á 5 mm of M3 bolt held with a pair of tweezers.

Figure 6: Experiments with three dimensional objects.

4.1.2 Circle sizes

Figure 7 shows some of the experiments with circles of various sizes. The general observation was that an Airy pattern become more visible with decreasing radius.

(a) Circle with diameter 0.3 mm. (b) Circle with diameter 0.8 mm. (c) Circle with diameter 1.5 mm. (d) Circle with diameter 3.0 mm.

Figure 7: Experiments with series of circles with increasing diameter.

4.2 Simulations

In all gray scale color plots, black represents the value zero and white is the maximum value. This means that the range differs slightly between each plot. The maximum value is denoted in the figure caption and is typically found in a point along the edge of the object. To distinguish the spots inside the shadow for some simulations the logarithm of the values are plotted with an orange color scheme.

In figure 8 different shapes with the same axis of symmetry are shown. It is seen that the symmetries can be seen in the diffraction pattern. The sharp corners of the star shapes leads to brighter dots.

(a) Square with maximum width 1.5 mm after 0.1 m propagation, $I_{\max} = 1.12$.
 (b) Four edged star with maximum width 1.5 mm after 0.1 m propagation, $I_{\max} = 1.32$.
 (c) Pentagon with maximum width 1.5 mm after 0.1 m propagation, $I_{\max} = 1.0$.
 (d) Five edged star with maximum width 1.5 mm after 0.1 m propagation, $I_{\max} = 1.66$.

Figure 8: Propagation of shapes with several axis of symmetry.

Some of the propagated distances are shown in figure 9. An Airy pattern becomes more visible with increasing propagation distance.

(a) Simulated circle at 0.05 m.
 (b) Simulated circle at 0.1 m.
 (c) Simulated circle at 0.25 m.
 (d) Simulated circle at 0.50 m.

Figure 9: Simulations to different distances for a circle with radius 1.5 mm.

4.3 Comparisons of experimental data, simulations and simplified Model

In figure 10 it is clear that two bright spots appear and the distance between them increases when the length of the minor axis decreases, both in the experiments and the simplified model although rays originating at the point are more visible in the simplified model.

(a) Ellipse with major axis 0.75 mm and minor axis 0.35 mm.
 (b) Prediction using simplified model of figure 10a.
 (c) Ellipse with major axis 0.75 mm and minor axis 0.65 mm.
 (d) Prediction using simplified model of figure 10c.

Figure 10: Experiments and predictions of ellipses with increasing size of minor axis.

Figure 11, 12 and 13 shows comparisons between experiments, simulations and the simplified

model. The smaller patterns in the simulations are not easily visible. If it is plotted with a logarithmic scale it shows an Airy-like pattern similar to the simplified model.

Figure 11: Experiments, simulations and predictions on a circle with diameter 1.5 mm.

Figure 12: Experiments, simulations and predictions on a five edged star shape with maximum width 1.5 mm.

Figure 13: Experiments, simulations and predictions on a heart shape with maximum width 1.5 mm.

4.4 Phase retrieval

For the simulations, unless specified, the entire simulated diffraction field was taken as an input, as shown in figure 16b, whereas the entire input is shown for the experimental results in figure 14a and 14c. In figure 14 the reversal of the experimental results are shown. The algorithm is able to recognize that it is one solid object, i.e. it filters out the diffraction inside the shadow, but fails to trace the correct contour.

(a) Circle with diameter 0.6 mm. Photographed at an angle. (b) Reversal of circle using HIO-ER algorithm. (c) Square with side length 1.5 mm. Photographed without any angle. (d) Reversal of square using HIO-ER algorithm.

Figure 14: Reversal of experimental results using HIO-ER algorithm.

In figure 15 the reversal of simulated results are shown. The algorithm successfully traced the contour with high precision, even for complicated shapes. The interior of the contours is however a varying field instead of being constant.

(a) Heart propagated 0.1 m using simulations, $I_{\max} = 1.18$. (b) Reversal of heart using HIO-ER. (c) IPT logo propagated 0.1 m using simulations, $I_{\max} = 1.89$. (d) Reversal of IPT logo using HIO-ER.

Figure 15: Reversal of simulated results using HIO-ER algorithm.

4.4.1 Sensitivity of Phase Reversal

The Gaussian beam in the simulations was changed to three times the original beam waist as well as scaled down by a factor of three. It was noted that this did not change the diffraction pattern more than the absolute intensities. In figure 16 the reversal algorithms sensitivity was tested by distorting the simulated result. The algorithm is still able to trace the contour of the circle, however the contour is not as sharp as the original reversal.

(a) Entire field image. (b) Reversal of full image, zoomed in. (c) Figure 16a cropped and added shot noise. (d) Reversal of shot noise and cropped

Figure 16: The HIO-ER algorithm applied to a simulated circle with radius 1.5 mm and the same simulation with decreased contrast and added shot noise.

5 Discussion

In this section, the discrepancies between the experimental results and simulations will be discussed. Further, the proposed model and reversal algorithm will be related to the original problem statement.

5.1 Comparison with experimental and simulated setup

The experimental pictures had a comparatively low resolution of the diffractive phenomena itself. This was partially due to the camera being held by a person, which led to the shutter speed being comparatively short, meaning smaller bright spots could not be captured. It was often the case that more details were visible to the naked eye than what were captured by the camera. The photos also had to be taken from a slight angle to not interfere with the laser which made direct comparisons with simulated propagation harder. Figure 14c was carefully taken to minimize the angle of the photo, however the camera sensor used was inferior to the phone camera used in other experiments. Using the phone camera at the same location was not possible for practical reasons.

The size of the diffractive patterns were expanded by using a lens. This meant that the light hit the object at an angle. An geometrical optics approximation with measures and lens described in section 3.1 results in the ray hitting the edge of an object with diameter 1.5 mm with an angle of 0.16° . For three dimensional objects with complex shapes, this could change the projected area somewhat. The phases of the Huygen sources originating at the edge of the object may also change. This is not captured in the simulations and is one potential reason for the deviation from the experimental results.

The spherical waves in the simulations are all coherent, just like a laser. Indeed, the problem statement from [1] does not specify any other properties of the light other than it being coherent. Since the light sources in the experimental and simulated setups are fundamentally different, it is expected that they will deviate from each other but still result in the same phenomena.

5.2 Using simplified model for reversing

In section 4.3 it is shown that equation 3 in many cases give a similar pattern as both the experiments as well as the simulations. This is to be expected since if $U(x,y,0)$ in the Rayleigh-Sommerfeld integral, equation 1, would be assumed to be constant along the edges of the simulated shape and zero elsewhere, the intensity $\|U\|^2$ would be similar to equation 3. The key difference is that equation 3 does not take the propagation distance into account. Indeed, it is observed in figure 9 that the pattern itself does not change, only that it becomes more diffuse. Therefore it is expected that the shape itself would be enough to get a rough approximation of the pattern. Further, the different distances simulated in 9 behaves similar to the different sizes tested in the experiments seen in figure 7, i.e. smaller radius in experiments or longer simulated distance leads to a more pronounced Airy pattern. This suggests that a model capturing a more fundamental shape of the pattern could be constructed.

The model is sensitive to resolution and the discretization process used. If the resolution is increased, the points would get smaller and harder to observe. Especially the checkerboard-like part of the pattern would become less visible.

5.3 Limitations with the two dimensional reduction

This report primarily investigated the diffraction pattern from two dimensional objects. This is partially due to practical reasons and partially due to the theoretical investigation in section 2.1.2 which showed that large changes in the three dimensional shape would result in small changes in the diffraction pattern. Machining and aligning regular three dimensional objects is significant practical problem and was not feasible with the available equipment.

However, in figure 6 a central spot is visible both for a cylinder and a sphere. Indeed, it was also reproduced with spheres of other radii, not showcased in this report. The cuboid in figure 6c shows a similar pattern to the simulated pattern in figure 8a, although due to the difference in size and the uneven edges on the cuboid, the diffraction pattern is not fully resolved.

5.4 Using phase retrieval as reverse algorithm

The phase retrieval algorithm was successful in tracing the contour of simulated propagation but failed to fully identify that the interior of the blockage had a constant attenuation. This is most likely due to the fact that the simulations are based on a scalar field, which does not propagate the same way as a laser would, which was the preset from `pyphase`[11] used in this study. The performance of the algorithm deteriorates when cropping the image and adding shot noise as in figure 16c and the problem with perspective in the used diffraction data further inhibits the algorithm from reversing the diffraction pattern.

5.5 Future work

The main limitation of this report was to experimentally investigate three dimensional shapes and fully resolving the phenomena experimentally. A way to increase the resolution would be to direct the laser directly into a camera sensor. Using such pictures, the HIO-ER reversal algorithms showed promising results in this study could thus be further investigated. A more refined experimental setup would give pictures with a resolution more similar to the simulations used in this study, and as such would likely be able to reversed with the HIO-ER algorithm.

The simplified model proposed here only depends of geometrical properties and the wavelength of the light. Since the algorithm is able to compute the intensity at individual points, independent of others, it could be possible to use a set of intensity at points, such as Arago spots and correlate that to a set of possible shapes.

6 Conclusions

This study has investigated diffraction in the context of the Arago-Poisson spot. Theoretical and experimental results suggest that the two-dimensional projected area of a three-dimensional shape is sufficient to determine its diffractive shadow. Based on this a simplified two-dimensional model centered around the Huygen source interaction with an objects edges was proposed. This model was primarily verified with simulations using the Rayleigh-Sommerfeld integral which were further verified with experimental data. The diffractive pattern of simulations and experiments were reversed using the Hybrid Input Output Error Reduction-algorithm (HIO-ER) implemented by the Python library `Pyphase`. The simplified modeled was successful in predicting the location of local maxima similar to the Arago-Poisson spot within the shadow of an arbitrary object. The HIO-ER algorithm was able to reverse the contour of an arbitrary shape from the simulation data with high precision, but performed worse on experimental data. The performance on experimental data is expected to improve significantly using a more refined experimental setup.

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